

Thermodynamic Functions of some Acryl Derivatives

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Complete fundamental frequencies of acrolein, ($\text{CH}_2=\text{CHCHO}$), methyl vinyl ketone ($\text{CH}_2=\text{CHCOCH}_3$), acrylamide ($\text{CH}_2=\text{CHCONH}_2$) and *N,N*-deuterated acrylamide ($\text{CH}_2=\text{CHCOND}_2$) have been taken from the infrared and Raman spectra of the respective compounds. The barrier height (V^*) due to the internal rotation of $-\text{COR}$ ($\text{R}=\text{H}, \text{CH}_3, \text{NH}_2$ or ND_2) top along $=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{C}$ single bond have been calculated from the knowledge of molecular geometry and the observed torsional frequencies. Because of intermediate values of V^* , the hindering internal rotation around the $\text{C}-\text{C}$ single bond for the molecules has been considered and the corrections to various thermodynamic functions are applied with the help of Pitzer and Gwinn's Tables. Thermodynamic functions, viz. enthalpy function, free energy function, entropy and heat capacity for these molecules have been computed at a pressure of 1 atm in the temperature range 100–1500 K under the rigid rotor harmonic oscillator approximation. Contributions to the thermodynamic functions due to anharmonicity have been calculated over the temperature range 300–1500 K by considering the molecules as anharmonic oscillators.

ONE of the important applications of vibrational spectroscopy of polyatomic molecules is the calculations of their thermodynamic functions, such as enthalpy function, heat capacity, free energy function and entropy, which are of practical importance, particularly in the study of chemical kinetics and chemical equilibria. Direct measurements by experiments of these quantities are usually difficult and sometimes, not even possible.

In the present work, barriers to internal rotation about the $=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{C}$ single bond and twisting about the $\text{C}=\text{C}$ double bond has been calculated for acrolein (AC), methyl vinyl ketone (MV), acrylamide (Ac-d_0) and *N,N*-deuterated acrylamide (Ac-d_2) from the knowledge of molecular geometry and the torsional frequencies. The vibrational frequencies (3N-6) for AC, MV, Ac-d_0 and Ac-d_2 have been taken from the literature¹⁻³. The spectroscopic data have been examined and utilised to compute the thermodynamic functions of these compounds statistically under the rigid rotor harmonic oscillator approximation and also by treating the molecules as anharmonic oscillators.

Method: The total energy of a system is given by

$$E = \epsilon_{\text{trans}} + \epsilon_{\text{rot}} + \epsilon_{\text{vib}} + \epsilon_{\text{elec}} \quad (1)$$

where, the subscripts trans, rot, vib and elec stand for translational, rotational, vibrational and electronic, respectively.

The partition function Q in terms of energy is given by

$$Q = \sum g_i \exp(-\epsilon_i/kT) = Q_{\text{trans}} \cdot Q_{\text{rot}} \cdot Q_{\text{vib}} \cdot Q_{\text{elec}} \quad (2)$$

where, g_i is the statistical weight of the energy level, k the Boltzmann constant and T the absolute temperature. The partition function for each type of energy may be evaluated separately from

equation (2) and then the corresponding thermodynamic functions are calculated. The contributions to the thermodynamic functions from the different types of partitions functions are then added to get the total value. The electronic contribution is small and ignored because ϵ_{elec} is large compared to kT at ordinary temperatures. For other remaining partition functions the standard expressions⁴ have been used and their contributions to thermodynamic functions have been calculated at various temperatures at the pressure of 1 atmosphere.

Considering the molecules as anharmonic oscillators, the anharmonicity constant for various modes of frequencies have been estimated approximately by the method given by Boobyer and Cox⁵. Contribution to the thermodynamic functions due to anharmonicity have been calculated by using the standard expressions⁶.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of available spectroscopic data of the polyatomic molecules AC, MV, Ac-d_0 and Ac-d_2 , it is possible to compute statistically their thermodynamic properties with fair degree of accuracy. Such calculations provide the unique method to obtain data for the molecules in which no such data could be obtained by direct measurements.

The atomic masses and other structural parameters¹⁻³ used in the calculations are given in Table 1. In computing the principal moments of inertia, all the molecules have been considered as planar ($x-y$ plane) with C_s symmetry and overall symmetry of the molecules has been taken as 1. The principal moments of inertia for each molecule are given in Table 2. All the four molecules (carbonyl

group substitution is regarded as point mass) possess two rotational tops, one due to rotation of CH_3 top along $\text{C}=\text{C}$ double bond and the other due to rotation of CHO , $\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)\text{O}$, $\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)\text{O}$ or

TABLE 1—STRUCTURAL PARAMETERS USED IN CALCULATING MOMENTS OF INERTIA

Bond	Length Å	Angle (degree)	Atom	Mass $\times 10^{30}$ kg
O—C	1.47	C—O—C 119.8	H	0.1674
C=O	1.24	C—O=O 123.2	D	0.3344
O=O	1.24	O—C—CH ₃ 115.1	C	1.9945
O—H	1.08	O—C—N 114.8	N	2.3259
O—H _{ald}	1.11	O—C—H _{ald} 115.1	O	2.6568
O—CH ₃	1.52	O=C—H 122.8		
O—N	1.32	O—C—H 110.3		
N—H	1.07			
N—D	1.07			

 TABLE 2—CALCULATED MOMENTS OF INERTIA IN (kg-m²) FOR AC, MV, Ac-d₀ AND Ac-d₂

Molecule	I_x $\times 10^{47}$	I_y $\times 10^{47}$	I_z $\times 10^{47}$
$\text{CH}_3=\text{CH}-\text{CHO}$	18.04	178.47	196.51
$\text{CH}_3=\text{CH}-\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)\text{O}$	85.52	184.39	269.91
$\text{CH}_3=\text{CH}-\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)\text{O}$	87.61	192.85	270.45
$\text{CH}_3=\text{CH}-\text{C}(\text{ND}_2)\text{O}$	91.81	205.84	287.64

$\text{C}(\text{ND}_2)\text{O}$ top along $=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{C}$ single bond. Here if the barrier height (V^*) is very large, the corresponding rotational frequency can be treated like any other vibrational frequency. Twisting about the double bond, as in the present case, falls in this category and hence $\text{C}=\text{C}$ torsion of AC, MV, Ac-d₀ and Ac-d₂ has been taken as simple fundamental frequency in the calculation. The potential function hindering internal rotation around the $=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{C}$ single bond in conjugated molecules has been discussed⁷. For all the four molecules, the total barrier height (V^*) has been calculated, where V^* is defined as

$$V^* = V_1 + 4V_2 + 9V_3 \quad (3)$$

The $0 \rightarrow 1$ torsional transition is related to V^* by the expression

$$V^* = \nu^2/F \text{ and } F (\text{cm}^{-2}) = 16.852/I_r (\text{amu-Å}^2) \quad (4)$$

where, ν is torsional fundamental frequency, I_r the reduced moment of inertia for the torsion about the axis of internal rotation and F , a reduced moment of inertia constant. The values of F were computed by using the method of Pitzer⁸. If V^* is of intermediate value, the vibrational degree of freedom corresponding to hindered internal rotation has been omitted from the vibrational partition function and instead an appropriate term has been added.

In the case of free internal rotation there is an additional factor Q_t , given by Herzberg⁹,

$$Q_t = (8\pi^2 I_r kT)^{1/2} / nh \quad (5)$$

where, n is the number of potential minima per revolution.

The barrier height (V^*) due to rotation of $\text{CHO}/\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)\text{O}$ tops along $=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{C}$ single bond have been calculated as 76.15 and 98.0 kJ mol⁻¹ for AC and MV, respectively. Similar quantities have been reported as 65.70 and 88.7 kJ mol⁻¹ on the basis of microwave measurements⁷. The V^* values for $\text{C}-\text{C}$ torsion are 47.80 and 49.43 kJ mol⁻¹ which correspond to Ac-d₀ and Ac-d₂, respectively. Because of intermediate values of V^* , the hindering internal rotation around the $=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{C}$ single bond for Ac-d₀ and Ac-d₂ has been considered and the corrections to various thermodynamic functions are applied with the help of Pitzer and Gwinn's Tables¹⁰. Full programme in Fortran IV has been made and used on CDC-316 computer for the calculations of I_r , F and V^* , as well as the thermodynamic functions.

The computed values of the various thermodynamic functions, viz. $(H^\circ - E_0^\circ)/T$, $-(G^\circ - E_0^\circ)/T$, C_p° and S° , for AC, MV, Ac-d₀ and Ac-d₂ are given in Table 3 at various temperatures ranging from 100–1500 K by treating the molecules as rigid rotor harmonic oscillators as well as anharmonic oscillators. The contribution to the thermodynamic functions due to anharmonicity is quite appreciable for temperatures above 300 K. It is seen that anharmonic oscillator behaves like a harmonic oscillator at low temperatures, and as the tempera-

 TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS (J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹) OF ACROLEIN, METHYL VINYL KETONE, ACRYLAMIDE AND N,N-DEUTERATED-ACRYLAMIDE

Temp K	$(H^\circ - E_0^\circ)/T$		$-(G^\circ - E_0^\circ)/T$		S°		C_p°	
	AC	MV	AC	MV	AC	MV	AC	MV
	Harmonic oscillator approximation							
100	95.85	97.23	188.07	199.67	223.92	236.90	40.80	43.58
200	41.34	44.60	214.53	227.63	255.87	272.23	53.48	60.84
300	47.91	53.00	232.51	247.29	280.42	300.29	68.84	78.57
400	55.07	61.42	247.26	263.69	302.33	325.11	84.01	94.40
600	69.03	76.67	272.27	291.56	341.30	368.23	109.51	118.28
800	81.20	89.19	293.84	315.39	375.04	404.59	125.90	134.20
1000	91.46	99.86	313.10	336.43	404.56	435.79	138.53	145.32
1500	110.71	117.74	354.08	380.46	464.79	498.20	157.55	161.61

(Table 3 contd.)

	Ac-d ₅	Ac-d ₄	Ac-d ₀	Ac-d ₄	Ac-d ₀	Ac-d ₄	Ac-d ₀	Ac-d ₄
100	38.42	38.46	210.05	211.42	218.47	249.88	44.88	45.62
200	45.61	46.85	241.34	243.31	286.95	290.16	64.15	68.36
300	55.29	57.74	262.87	265.03	318.16	322.77	89.13	94.77
400	66.06	69.28	279.90	282.84	345.96	352.12	112.91	118.82
600	86.71	90.76	311.23	315.85	397.94	406.61	149.24	155.26
800	104.21	108.71	338.13	343.68	442.34	452.39	173.82	179.92
1000	118.68	123.42	362.76	369.55	481.44	492.97	191.26	197.07
1500	145.23	150.02	416.64	425.30	561.87	575.32	217.12	221.49
	AC	MV	AC	MV	AC	MV	AC	MV
300	48.49	53.90	232.78	247.75	281.27	301.65	69.31	79.33
400	56.03	62.87	247.75	264.48	303.78	327.35	85.01	95.31
600	70.93	79.40	273.32	293.18	344.25	372.58	109.69	119.58
800	84.17	93.33	295.58	317.98	379.75	411.31	127.35	135.71
1000	95.58	104.97	315.62	340.10	411.20	445.07	140.13	146.89
1500	117.84	127.12	358.84	387.11	476.68	514.23	159.15	163.07
	Ac-d ₀	Ac-d ₄	Ac-d ₀	Ac-d ₄	Ac-d ₀	Ac-d ₄	Ac-d ₀	Ac-d ₀
300	56.51	58.99	263.55	265.70	320.06	324.69	89.86	95.65
400	67.97	71.27	280.99	283.94	348.96	355.21	114.10	120.15
600	90.27	94.51	313.32	318.00	403.59	412.51	151.20	157.29
800	109.64	114.43	341.41	347.09	451.05	461.52	176.18	182.39
1000	126.08	131.22	367.36	374.35	493.44	505.57	193.74	199.55
1500	157.75	163.17	424.93	433.98	582.63	597.15	219.47	223.73

Fig. 1. Variation of thermodynamic functions with absolute temperature for acrolein and methyl vinyl ketone.

ture rises the contribution due to anharmonicity increases. The variation of the thermodynamic functions with absolute temperature are represented by curves in Figs. 1 and 2. The thermodynamic

functions rise more rapidly in the low temperature range and less rapidly in the high temperature range. The trend of variation with temperature is similar to that reported in literature¹¹.

Fig. 2. Variation of thermodynamic functions with absolute temperature for acrylamide and N,N -deuterated-acrylamide

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